

An Evaluation of Listening Strategy Instruction Intervention among EFL Learners at Thai Nguyen University

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ABSTRACT: The study was conducted at two institutions (The International School and The College of Education) Thai Nguyen University. The total number of participants was 92. The study employs a quasi-experimental research design to evaluate the effectiveness of a listening strategy instruction invention towards the listening comprehension. The findings reveals that students use listening strategies at a low level ($M=2.1$). The results also confirmed that the listening intervention really helped students in their listening ability. The mean of pre-test was $M=3.72$. After four weeks of intervention the mean scores were $M=4.96$ for the experimental group and $M= 3.83$ for the control group. After another four weeks, the improvement of the experimental group was $M=5.6$ compared to $M=4.54$ in the control group. At the end of the intervention the improvement the mean scores for experimental group and control group were $M=6.41$ and $M=5.45$ respectively. From the findings, it is concluded that the listening strategy intervention really improve students' listening comprehension.

KEYWORDS: Language teaching; teaching listening, evaluation, listening strategies, cognitive, metacognitive strategies listening intervention

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the study

Listening, undoubtedly, plays an important role in successful communications between interlocutors. It is estimated that adults spend communicating involves listening time of 45%, a percentage that dominates time spent engaged in the other three skills: writing 9%; reading 16%; and speaking 30% (Feyten, 1991; Nunan, 1998; Flowerdew & Miller, 2005 cited in Siegel, 2015). Another study revealed that of their total communicating time, college students spent an average of 14% writing, 16% speaking, 17% reading, and a whopping 53% listening (Adler & Rodman, 2006. p. 116). The importance attributed to listening continues to increase in international testing, business, and communication (Richards & Burns, 2012 cited in Siegel, 2015, p. 5).

The contribution of listening to communication is obviously enormous. However, the teaching and researching of listening comprehension are not adequately received attention in EFL contexts. Nunan (1997, p. 47) even described listening as 'the *Cinderella* skill in second language learning'. The complexity associated with understanding listening is one reason why there is a neglect of research about listening (Rowley-Jolivet, 2002). The 'low profile of listening research' is further accentuated in the specific case of listening in university or academic environments (Lynch, 2011, p. 78). Learners of English as a foreign language often complain that listening is the most challenging skill regardless of how much effort had been made. It is easy to see that a typical listening lesson has not changed so much in the past 20 years. The teachers do some pre-listening and then have students listen to the text and perform a variety of tasks. Teachers evaluate students' comprehension based on the correctness of their responses and proceed to the next activity. The old-fashioned way of teaching and learning listening comprehension makes it even frustrated by both teachers and learners.

Literature shows little evidence that teachers instruct students in listening strategies in order to help them master listening in the language classroom. Mendelsohn (1995) claims teachers feel unprepared to teach such skills. Textbook publishing companies have not provided enough support in teaching listening strategies; nor have they changed their stance in regard to listening activities, which remain "traditional in approach, content and organization" (Vandergrift, 2003, p. 426). The listening tasks typically require students to respond to multiple choice or true or false questions after a listening task rather than defining the activity instructional goal and type of response expected from the student. Learners are merely exposed to the spoken language, but they do little to improve learners' listening comprehension. Listening has not been viewed as a skill, "but as an activity to be used in the foreign language instruction" (Feyten, 1991, p. 175).

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This study attempts to evaluate the effectiveness (if any) of the so-called “A listening strategy instruction intervention” program applied to EFL learners at Thai Nguyen University, Vietnam. Hopefully, the instructions of listening strategies which were defined as ways of listening that were planned and consciously adopted would improve comprehension among EFL students at Thai Nguyen University.

1.2. A statement of research purposes

The first aim of the study is to examine the uses of listening strategies reported by students of non-English major at Thai Nguyen University. The second aim is to evaluate the effectiveness of the listening strategies instructions towards listening achievement. It is assumed that the application of appropriate strategies during a listening lesson would help learners better comprehend the listening discourses.

1.3. Research questions

The present study attempts to find the answers to the following research questions;

1.3.1. *What level of frequency of listening strategies reported using by EFL students at Thai Nguyen University?*

1.3.2. *Is there a statistically significant difference in listening comprehension scores between students who are explicitly taught listening strategies and those who are not?*

1.4 Significance of the study

Firstly, the study may contribute to the literature of teaching listening comprehension in EFL context. Secondly, the findings of the study may act as a reference for teachers of English in their teaching practice to give strategic instructions during their teaching to help students better comprehend the spoken language. Last but not least, students can be beneficial from the study in terms of taking advantages of listening strategies delivered by teachers or instructors.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.5. The nature of spoken language

Listening and reading are referred to as receptive skills. However, reading is the process of extracting meaning from written texts which stay there for you to read and re-read. There are spaces between words for you to clarify the meaning. Listening is quite different. Listeners have to cope with flows of speech which seem to be non-stop. Spoken text is fragmented (loosely structured) and involved (interactive with the listener). Spoken discourse has also been described as having a linear structure, compared to a hierarchical structure for written text. Whereas the unit of organization of written text is the sentence, spoken language is usually delivered one clause at a time, and longer utterances in conversation generally consist of several coordinated clauses. Spoken texts are often context-dependent and personal, assuming shared background knowledge. Lastly, spoken texts may be spoken with many different accents, from standard or non-standard, regional, non-native, and so on. The difference between spoken and written language has made listening even more challenging for language learners in terms of comprehending the spoken texts (Richards, 2008; p.3). Table 1 demonstrates the differences between spoken text and written text (Flowerdew & Miller, 2005, p. 48).

Table 1: Distinctive linguistic features of spoken text and written text

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SPOKEN DISCOURSE	LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF WRITTEN TEXT
phonological contractions and assimilations	longer information units
hesitations, false starts, and filled pauses	complex relations of coordination and subordination
sentence fragments rather than complete sentences	high incidence of attributive adjectives
structured according to tone units rather than clauses	wider range and precise choice of vocabulary
frequent occurrence of discourse markers at beginning or end	high lexical density (nominalization)
tone groups	longer average word length
high incidence of questions and imperatives	more frequent use of passive voice
first and second person pronouns	high use of coherence and cohesive devices
deixis (reference outside the text)	

Davison (2009) refers to the difference between spoken language and written language in terms of register (i.e. from formal to informal), dialect (i.e. from standard English to regional), accents (i.e. from regional accents to received pronunciation), prosodic feature of the speech (i.e. tone, speed, rhythm). Hughes (2011) makes a distinction between spoken discourse and written discourse from production perspectives as context dependent vs. decontextualized; planned vs. unplanned; transient vs. non-transient; oral/aural vs. visual/motoric and dynamic vs. static (p. 11). It is true that a listener have to perform many invisible mental activities at the same time to comprehend the messages delivered by speakers that does not happen when dealing with written texts.

1.6. The required knowledge for listening comprehension

Listening has been conceptualized as “a process that involves the interpretation of messages that others have intentionally transmitted in the effort to understand those messages and respond to them appropriately” (Burlison, 2011, p. 27). The process consists of several stages; right after hearing, the next stage is *attending* - the act of paying attention to a signal. In the following stage, the *understanding*, the process of making sense of a message which consists of a grasp of the syntax of the language being spoken, semantic decoding, and knowledge of the pragmatic rules that help you figure out a speaker’s meaning from the context. After understanding, the *responding* phase comes. Responding to a message consists of giving observable feedback to the speaker. Offering feedback serves two important functions: It helps you clarify your understanding of a speaker’s message, and it shows that you care about what that speaker is saying. The final stage is *remembering* which decreases along the time (Adler & Rodman, 2006, p. 117). Flowerdew and Miller (2005) synthesize four main types of knowledge that a learners need to comprehend a spoken message, namely *phonological* - the sound system; *syntactic* - how words are put together; *semantic* - word and propositional knowledge; and *pragmatic* - the meaning of utterances in particular situations (p. 30). Rost (2011) shares the same view when identifies effective listeners are those who handle well on neurological processing, linguistic processing, semantic processing, and pragmatic processing. The issue of neurological refers to hearing mechanics which is not considered factors causing listening difficulty. The other areas such as linguistic, semantic and pragmatic are believed to hamper listeners from comprehension. Linguistic processing deals with phonological procedures involved in perceiving speech. Semantic processing refers to the process of making sense of what has been input. This involves the combination of listeners’ schemata and new information to construct new understanding of the message. Finally, pragmatic processing determines a higher level of comprehension i.e. the listeners have to utilize other conventions or inference to make sense of the meaning of the spoken language.

1.7. Listening strategies and their classification

Listening strategies are mental processes that language learners use in order to understand the oral texts (Vandergrift, 1999). These mental processes include selecting input, constructing meaning and relating existing knowledge to performing tasks (O’Malley et al., 1989; Rost, 2002). Among all the strategies for listening, O’Malley and Chamot (1990) claimed three main types of strategies: metacognitive, cognitive and social strategies.

1.7.1. Metacognitive strategies

The metacognitive strategy was a kind of self-regulated learning. It included the attempt to plan, check, monitor, select, revise, and evaluate, etc. For example, for metacognitive planning strategies, learners would clarify the objectives of an anticipated listening task, and attend to specific aspects of language input or situational details that assisted in understanding the task (Vandergrift, 1999). Generally, it can be discussed through pre-listening planning strategies, while-listening monitoring strategies, and post-listening evaluation strategies. According to Nowrouzi, et al., (2014), pre-listening strategy is the learners preparation for listening through manipulating the environment, focusing attention, applying advance organizer, selecting attention, and deciding to think in English. While-listening strategy is the learners’ focuses on monitoring their listening and attract their attention. Post-listening strategy is the evaluation of their understanding in listening and also tried to find out what they did to help their listening comprehension.

1.7.2. Cognitive strategies

The cognitive strategies are related to comprehending and storing input in working memory or long-term memory for later retrieval. They are investigated from the aspects of bottom-up strategies, top-down strategies. For bottom-up processing, it refers to using the incoming input as the basis for understanding the message. Comprehension begins with the received data that is analyzed as successive levels of organization-sounds, words, as a process of decoding (Richards, 2008; p. 4). On the other hand, top-down processing went from meaning to language. It refers to the use of background knowledge in understanding the meaning of a message. The background knowledge required for top-down processing may be previous knowledge about the topic of discourse, situational or contextual knowledge, or knowledge in the form of “schemata” or “scripts” plans about the overall structure of events and the relationships between them (Richards, 2008, p. 7).

1.7.3. Social - affective strategies

Social-affective strategy is divided in social strategy and affective strategy. Social strategy refers to sharing the idea to others to get the comprehension in listening and affective strategy refers to learners’ confidence during the listening process (Vandergrift, 1997). For social-affective strategies, Vandergrift (2003) defined the strategies as the techniques listeners used to collaborate with others, to verify understanding or to lower anxiety. Habte-Gabr (2006) stated that socio-affective strategies were those which were non academics in nature and involve stimulating learning through establishing a level of empathy between the instructor and student. They included considering factors such as emotions and attitudes (Oxford, 1990). It was essential for listeners to know how to reduce the anxiety, feel confident in doing listening tasks, and promote personal motivation in improving listening competence (Vandergrift, 1997).

In the present study these strategies were not part of the treatment. Social-affective strategies refer to those strategies that require the presence of another person in the listening process. They did not suit the scope of this research because listening activities were

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implemented as an interaction between the aural input and the learner through the exposure to audio stimuli and not as a face-to-face interaction with another speaker.

III. METHODOLOGY

1.8. Research design

Research design refers to the way a study is planned and conducted, the procedures and techniques employed to answer the research problem or question (McMillan & Schumacher, 1984). This study employed a quantitative Quasi-experimental pre-test-post-test design. The dependent variables in the study were the assessment of listening comprehension. The independent variable was the explicit instructions of cognitive and metacognitive listening strategies during a period of 12 weeks following the schedules of the institutions (The International School and The School of Foreign Language of Thai Nguyen University).

1.9. Participants

A total number of 92 first year students participated in the study. These students belong to two educational institutions at Thai Nguyen University. They are offered a one year of intensive English training course. After the course, they were expected to achieve an overall band of 5.5 in the IELTS examination to be placed in majoring studies. The students at the International School received explicit strategy instructions (Experimental group). The students at the School of Foreign Language did not receive strategy instructions (Control group). These students might not know the purposes of the study because they belong to different institutions in different campus. The description of the participants could be found in the table 2 below;

Table 2: Frequency Table for Nominal Variables

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Control Group (CG)		
female	22	23.91
male	23	25.00
Missing	0	0.00
Experimental Group (EG)		
female	20	21.73
male	27	29.34
Missing	0	0.00

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

1.10. Research instruments

In order to collect data for the study, questionnaires of listening strategies were administered to both groups to determine their overall uses of listening strategies during the first week of the semester. The questionnaire was the revised version of the Metacognitive Awareness Listening Questionnaire (MALQ) developed by Vandegrift (2008). The original version of the questionnaire consists of 21 items. However, the adopted version had been shortened to 20 items because the item 3 was not suitable for Vietnamese students (see appendix A). The items use a 5 point Likert Scale with the scores ranging from 1.0 - 2.4 (low level); 2.5 - 3.4 (medium level); 3.5 - 5.0 (high level). After the administration of the MALQ, the researcher conducted a simulated IELTS listening test to get the baseline of the listening ability in both groups. The results of the test would serve as the pre-test for the study. A careful plan of listening intervention, listening strategy instructions, would be prepared by the researcher to deliver to the experimental group.

1.11. Research procedures

During the first week of the semester, the researcher administered the Metacognitive Awareness Listening Questionnaire (MALQ) adopted from Vandergrift (2008). During the 12 weeks of the study, different listening strategies were introduced. The researcher conducted three more tests after each phase of the intervention for both groups to compare the difference between groups. The results served as post-test 1, post-test 2, and post-test 3. There would be Post-tests for experimental group (Post-test EG1, Post-test EG2, Post-test EG3 and control group Post-tests (Post-test CG1, Post-test CG2 and Post-test CG3)

IV. FINDINGS

1.12. Research question 1: *What level of frequency of listening strategies reported using by EFL students at Thai Nguyen University?*

A Cronbach alpha coefficient was calculated for the MALQ scale, consisting of MALQ 1, MALQ 2, MALQ 3, ... MALQ 20. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was evaluated using the guidelines suggested by George and Mallery (2016) where > .9 excellent, > .8 good, > .7 acceptable, > .6 questionable, > .5 poor, and ≤ .5 unacceptable.

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The items for MALQ had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.79, indicating acceptable reliability. Table 3 presents the results of the reliability analysis.

Table 3: Reliability Table for MALQ

Scale	No. of Items	α	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
MALQ	20	0.79	0.75	0.83

Note. The lower and upper bounds of Cronbach's α were calculated using a 95% confidence interval.

Table 4 presented the descriptive statistics from MALQ. It shows that EFL students at Thai Nguyen University use listening strategies at low level ($M=2.1$, $SD = 0.6$).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of MALQ

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
MALQ	92	1.05	3.30	2.1135	.59437
Valid N (list-wise)	92				

1.13. Research question 2: Is there a statistically significant difference in listening comprehension scores between students who are explicitly taught listening strategies and those who are not?

A two-tailed paired samples t -test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference of Pre-test and Post-test EG1 was significantly different from zero.

Assumptions

Normality. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether the differences in Pre-test and Post-test EG1 could have been produced by a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test were significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $W = 0.89$, $p < .001$. This result suggests the differences in Pre-test and Posttest_EG1 are unlikely to have been produced by a normal distribution, indicating the normality assumption is violated.

Homogeneity of Variance. Levene's test was conducted to assess whether the variances of Pre-test and Post-test EG1 were significantly different. The result of Levene's test for was not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $F(1, 182) = 2.02$, $p = .157$. This result suggests it is possible that Pre-test and Post-test EG1 were produced by distributions with equal variances, indicating the assumption of homogeneity of variance was met.

Results

The result of the two-tailed paired samples t -test was significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $t(91) = -8.31$, $p < .001$. This finding suggests the difference in the mean of Pre-test and the mean of Post-test EG1 was significantly different from zero. The mean of Pre-test was significantly lower than the mean of Post-test EG1. The results are presented in Table 5. A bar plot of the means is presented in Figure 1.

Table 5: Two-Tailed Paired Samples t -Test for the difference between Pre-test and Post-test EG1

Pre-test		Post-test EG1		t	p	d
M	SD	M	SD			
3.72	1.04	4.96	1.29	-8.31	< .001	0.87

Note. $N = 92$. Degrees of Freedom for the t -statistic = 91. d represents Cohen's d .

Figure 1: The means of Pre-test and Post-test EG1

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A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference of Pre-test and Post-test CG1 was significantly different from zero.

Assumptions

Normality. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether the differences in Pre-test and Post-test G1 could have been produced by a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test were significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $W = 0.92$, $p < .001$. This result suggests the differences in Pre-test and Post-test CG1 are unlikely to have been produced by a normal distribution, indicating the normality assumption is violated.

Homogeneity of Variance. Levene's test was conducted to assess whether the variances of Pre-test and Post-test CG1 were significantly different. The result of Levene's test for was not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $F(1, 182) = 1.32$, $p = .252$. This result suggests it is possible that Pre-test and Post-test CG1 were produced by distributions with equal variances, indicating the assumption of homogeneity of variance was met.

Results

The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $t(91) = -1.12$, $p = .266$. This finding suggests the difference in the mean of Pre-test and the mean of Post-test CG1 was not significantly different from zero. The results are presented in Table 6. A bar plot of the means is presented in Figure 2.

Table 6: Two-Tailed Paired Samples *t*-Test for the difference between Pre-test and Post-test CG1

Pre-test		Post-test_CG1		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
3.72	1.04	3.83	1.03	-1.12	.266	0.12

Note. $N = 92$. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 91. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 2: The means of Pre-test and Post-test CG1

A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference of Post-test EG2 and Post-test CG2 was significantly different from zero.

Assumptions

Normality. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether the differences in Post-test EG2 and Post-test CG2 could have been produced by a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test were significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $W = 0.90$, $p < .001$. This result suggests the differences in Post-test EG2 and Post-test CG2 are unlikely to have been produced by a normal distribution, indicating the normality assumption is violated.

Homogeneity of Variance. Levene's test was conducted to assess whether the variances of Post-test EG2 and Post-test CG2 were significantly different. The result of Levene's test for was significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $F(1, 182) = 5.91$, $p = .016$. This result suggests it is unlikely that Post-test EG2 and Post-test CG2 were produced by distributions with equal variances, indicating the assumption of homogeneity of variance was violated.

Results

The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $t(91) = 6.76$, $p < .001$. This finding suggests the difference in the mean of Post-test EG2 and the mean of Post-test CG2 was significantly different from zero. The mean

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of Post-test EG2 was significantly higher than the mean of Post-test CG2. The results are presented in Table 7. A bar plot of the means is presented in Figure 3.

Table 7: Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference between Post-test EG2 and Post-test CG2

Post-test EG2		Post-test CG2		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
5.60	0.85	4.54	1.10	6.76	< .001	0.70

Note. N = 92. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 91. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 3: The means of Post-test EG2 and Post-test CG2

A two-tailed paired samples t-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference of Post-test EG3 and Post-test CG3 was significantly different from zero.

Assumptions

Normality. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether the differences in Post-test EG3 and Post-test CG3 could have been produced by a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test were significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $W = 0.86$, $p < .001$. This result suggests the differences in Posttest_EG3 and Posttest_CG3 are unlikely to have been produced by a normal distribution, indicating the normality assumption is violated.

Homogeneity of Variance. Levene's test was conducted to assess whether the variances of Posttest_EG3 and Posttest_CG3 were significantly different. The result of Levene's test for was not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $F(1, 182) = 2.82$, $p = .095$. This result suggests it is possible that Posttest_EG3 and Posttest_CG3 were produced by distributions with equal variances, indicating the assumption of homogeneity of variance was met.

Results

The result of the two-tailed paired samples t-test was significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $t(91) = 10.51$, $p < .001$. This finding suggests the difference in the mean of Post-test EG3 and the mean of Post-test CG3 was significantly different from zero. The mean of Post-test EG3 was significantly higher than the mean of Post-test CG3. The results are presented in Table 8. A bar plot of the means is presented in Figure 4.

Table 8: Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the difference between Post-test EG3 and Post-test CG3

Post-test_EG3		Post-test_CG3		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
6.41	0.76	5.45	0.92	10.51	< .001	1.10

Note. N = 92. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 91. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 4: The means of Post-test EG3 and Post-test CG3

A two-tailed paired samples t-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference of Pre-test and Post-test EG3 was significantly different from zero.

Assumptions

Normality. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether the differences in Pre-test and Post-test EG3 could have been produced by a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test were significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $W = 0.89$, $p < .001$. This result suggests the differences in Pre-test and Post-test EG3 are unlikely to have been produced by a normal distribution, indicating the normality assumption is violated.

Homogeneity of Variance. Levene's test was conducted to assess whether the variances of Pretest and Posttest_EG3 were significantly different. The result of Levene's test for was significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $F(1, 182) = 18.68$, $p < .001$. This result suggests it is unlikely that Pre-test and Post-test EG3 were produced by distributions with equal variances, indicating the assumption of homogeneity of variance was violated.

Results

The result of the two-tailed paired samples t-test was significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $t(91) = -18.53$, $p < .001$. This finding suggests the difference in the mean of Pre-test and the mean of Post-test EG3 was significantly different from zero. The mean of Pre-test was significantly lower than the mean of Post-test EG3. The results are presented in Table 9. A bar plot of the means is presented in Figure 5.

Table 9: Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the difference between Pre-test and Post-test EG3

Pre-test		Post-test EG3		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
3.72	1.04	6.41	0.76	-18.53	< .001	1.93

Note. $N = 92$. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 91. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 5: The means of Pre-test and Post-test EG3

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A two-tailed paired samples t-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference of Pre-test and Post-test CG3 was significantly different from zero.

Assumptions

Normality. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether the differences in Pre-test and Post-test CG3 could have been produced by a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test were significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $W = 0.91$, $p < .001$. This result suggests the differences in Pre-test and Post-test CG3 are unlikely to have been produced by a normal distribution, indicating the normality assumption is violated.

Homogeneity of Variance. Levene's test was conducted to assess whether the variances of Pre-test and Post-test CG3 were significantly different. The result of Levene's test for was not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $F(1, 182) = 2.75$, $p = .099$. This result suggests it is possible that Pre-test and Post-test CG3 were produced by distributions with equal variances, indicating the assumption of homogeneity of variance was met.

Results

The result of the two-tailed paired samples t-test was significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $t(91) = -15.65$, $p < .001$. This finding suggests the difference in the mean of Pre-test and the mean of Post-test CG3 was significantly different from zero. The mean of Pre-test was significantly lower than the mean of Post-test CG3. The results are presented in Table 10. A bar plot of the means is presented in Figure 6.

Table 10: Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the difference between Pre-test and Post-test CG3

Pre-test		Post-test CG3		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
3.72	1.04	5.45	0.92	-15.65	< .001	1.63

Note. $N = 92$. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 91. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 6: The means of Pre-test and Post-test CG3

V. DISCUSSIONS

It is undeniable that listening has been overlooked in comparison with other language skills (Speaking, Reading and Writing). The skill has received the least amount of attention (Curtain & Pesola, 1994; Feyten, 1991; Mendelsohn, 1995). Teachers have just simply repeated the same procedure with a new text the next day. Siegel (2015) confessed that when teaching listening, he was doing very little ‘teaching.’ Instead, he was continually evaluating students’ existing listening ability, but was not providing much scaffolded guidance that would help students become competent listeners (p. 3). This reality is true for Vietnamese EFL context where most teachers believe that listening ability can be gained through massive exposure to spoken texts.

This study attempted to evaluate the effectiveness of listening strategies instructions on listening comprehension. The treatment consisted of an explicit instructional sequence of a strategies-based model implemented over a period of time. In this study, the researcher implemented a 12 week listening strategy intervention for a group of EFL learners at the International School – Thai Nguyen University. The results of the study reveals that the uses of listening strategies are reported at a low level ($M=2.1$). It meant that not many listening strategies are employed among participants. The results also confirmed that the intervention worked well for the experimental group ($N=47$). The mean score of the pre-test (the baseline for both groups) was $M=3.72$ in an IELTS simulation listening test. The intervention focused on metacognitive strategies, i.e. the planning strategies and cognitive strategies, i.e. top down processing and bottom up processing. After first four weeks, the means of post-test1 were $M=4.96$ and $M=3.83$ for experimental

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group and control group respectively. There was a significant difference between the mean of pre-test and post-test1 for the experimental group (M=3.72 compared to M=4.96), while the control group showed a little improvement (M=3.72 compared to M=3.83) the difference was not significant. After another four weeks, the difference in the mean scores of the experimental group were far more than the mean scores of the control group, M=5.56 and M=4.45 respectively. By the twelfth week of the intervention, the mean of post-test 3 of the experimental group reached M=6.41, the mean for control group was M=5.54. The difference of the mean scores in the pre-test and post-test revealed a significant improvement in both groups. However, the experimental group showed a greater improvement, M=6.41 and M=5.54 respectively. The findings from the study can be used as a reference for language teachers in Vietnam to pay more attention to the teaching of listening comprehension, especially for students at the International School, Thai Nguyen University where the language of instruction for all disciplines is delivered in English.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The aims of the present study were to examine the uses of listening strategies reported by first year students at two institutions at Thai Nguyen University (The International School and The School of Foreign Language). The results showed that these participants use listening strategies at low level (2.1 out of 5). The study also confirmed the effectiveness of listening strategies instructions on listening comprehension. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher suggests that teachers should take advantages of listening strategies in order to make the teaching of listening comprehension more effective rather than exposing students with spoken texts again and again.

VII. LIMITATIONS

The study was conducted in a small with only 92 participants (47 for experimental group, and 45 for control group). The finding might not be sufficiently generalizable for all the first year students at Thai Nguyen University. We hope that there will be further studies on the topic to give comprehensive insights of teaching listening comprehension for teachers as well as students.

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APPENDIX A: Metacognitive Awareness Listening Questionnaires (MALQ)

Adapted from Vandergrift and Tafaghodtari (2010 as cited Abdalhamid, 2012)

#	Statements	Rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
	Before listening, I prepare my mind to concentrate	1	2	3	4	5
	Before listening, I request myself to make progress	1	2	3	4	5
	Before I start to listen, I have a plan in my head for how I am going to listen	1	2	3	4	5
	While listening, I do not understand if I am unfamiliar with speakers' accents	1	2	3	4	5
	While listening, I will check what part of content I do not understand	1	2	3	4	5
	While listening, I will double check again for my answer	1	2	3	4	5
	I am aware of my inattention and correct it while doing listening test	1	2	3	4	5
	I try to listen for specific details to see whether I can understand them	1	2	3	4	5
	After listening, I think back to how I listened and about what I might do differently next time.	1	2	3	4	5
	After Listening, I think back to the quality of my strategy use (for example planning, inferencing) and about how I can do better next time	1	2	3	4	5
	After listening, I reflect on my problems, such as the key words that I do not understand	1	2	3	4	5
	After listening, I evaluate how much I could understand	1	2	3	4	5
	While listening, I will notice the questions with who, how, when, where and what in the content.	1	2	3	4	5
	While listening, I try to understand each word	1	2	3	4	5
	While listening, I repeat words or phrases softly or mentally	1	2	3	4	5
	While listening, I piece things together from the details	1	2	3	4	5
	I take notes of main points and keywords	1	2	3	4	5
	I listen for main ideas first and then details	1	2	3	4	5
	I predict or make hypotheses on text by titles	1	2	3	4	5
	I can guess the meaning based on the context	1	2	3	4	5